

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Approximate solution of the I kind Fredholm singular integral equations

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Problems are frequently solved using differential and integral equations in fields such as mechanics, hydrodynamics, aerodynamics, electrodynamics, quantum mechanics, and the theory of elasticity, as well as various other areas of technology. These equations are studied in the course of mathematical physics in science. It is well known that the main boundary value problems for the Laplace equation, namely the Dirichlet and Neumann problems, are solved using the potentials of simple and double layers. These boundary value problems lead to singular integral equations with Cauchy kernel, Hilbert kernel and singularity of a higher order. Analytical solutions of singular integral equations are represented by singular integrals [1-3]. The antiderivative function of the singular integral in the analytical solution can be found in some cases. Obtaining approximate methods for calculating such singular integrals with high accuracy is one of the important tasks of computational mathematics.

In the work [4] is considered a singular integral equation

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\phi(x)}{x-t} dx = \varphi(t), \quad t \in (-1, 1). \quad (1)$$

Let us recall the definition of singular integrals in the sense of principal value of Cauchy.

The principal Cauchy value of the special integral $\int_a^b \frac{\phi(x)}{x-t} dx$, $a < t < b$ is the limit

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\int_a^{t-\varepsilon} \frac{\phi(x)}{x-t} dx + \int_{t+\varepsilon}^b \frac{\phi(x)}{x-t} dx \right],$$

if it exists.

It is known that if a function ϕ on the interval $[a, b]$ satisfies the Hölder condition with exponent α ($0 < \alpha \leq 1$) and coefficient A , i.e. if

$$|\phi(x_1) - \phi(x_2)| \leq A|x_1 - x_2|^\alpha,$$

then there exists the integral $\int_a^b \frac{\phi(x)}{x-t} dx$, $a < t < b$.

Equation (1) has four distinct solutions expressed as follows:

Case I: The function $\phi(t)$ is bounded within a certain range at the two endpoints of t , which are $t = -1$ and $t = 1$, then a solution of (1) is

$$\phi_1(t) = -\frac{\sqrt{1-t^2}}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\varphi(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(x-t)} dx, \quad (2)$$

provided that

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\varphi(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx = 0.$$

Case II: The function $\phi(t)$ is bounded at the end $t = 1$, but unbounded at the end $t = -1$, then a solution of (1) is

$$\phi_2(t) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1-t}{1+t}} \int_{-1}^1 \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}} \frac{\varphi(x)}{x-t} dx, \quad (3)$$

Case III: The function $\phi(t)$ is bounded at the end $t = -1$, but unbounded at the end $t = 1$, then

$$\phi_3(t) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1+t}{1-t}} \int_{-1}^1 \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{1+x}} \frac{\varphi(x)}{x-t} dx, \quad (4)$$

Case IV: The function $\phi(t)$ is unbounded at both the endpoints $t = \pm 1$,

$$\phi_4(t) = -\frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{1-t^2}} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sqrt{1-x^2}\varphi(x)}{x-t} dx + \frac{C}{\sqrt{1-t^2}}, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\int_{-1}^1 \phi(t) dx = C.$$

For this purpose, the approximate calculation of singular integrals (2)-(5) is sufficient.

Several methods have been developed for the calculation of the singular integrals (2)-(5). They are: Discrete vortex method, Interpolation methods, Piecewise interpolation method and other numerical quadrature methods. We consider the following quadrature formula

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\omega_i(x)\varphi(x)}{x-t} dx \cong \sum_{\alpha=0}^{m-1} \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\alpha,i}[\beta] \varphi^{(\alpha)}(x_\beta - 1), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\omega_1(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}, \quad \omega_2(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1+x}{1-x}}, \quad \omega_3(x) = \sqrt{\frac{1-x}{1+x}}, \quad \omega_4(x) = \sqrt{1-x^2},$$

with the error functional

$$\ell_i(x) = \frac{\omega_i(x)\varepsilon_{[-1,1]}(x)}{x-t} - \sum_{\alpha=0}^{m-1} \sum_{\beta=0}^N (-1)^\alpha C_{\alpha,i}[\beta] \delta^{(\alpha)}(x-x_\beta+1), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \quad (7)$$

where $-1 < t < 1$, $C_{\alpha,i}[\beta]$ are the coefficients, $x_\beta - 1 \in [-1, 1]$ are the nodes, N is a natural number, $\varepsilon_{[-1,1]}(x)$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[-1, 1]$, δ is the Dirac delta function, φ is a function of the space $L_2^{(m)}(-1, 1)$. Here $L_2^{(m)}(-1, 1)$ is the Sobolev space of functions with a square integrable m th generalized derivative and equipped with the norm

$$\|\varphi\|_{L_2^{(m)}(-1, 1)} = \left\{ \int_{-1}^1 (\varphi^{(m)}(x))^2 dx \right\}^{1/2}$$

and $\int_{-1}^1 (\varphi^{(m)}(x))^2 dx < \infty$.

Since the functional ℓ of the form (7) is defined on the space $L_2^{(m)}(-1, 1)$ it is necessary to impose the following conditions (see [5])

$$(\ell_i, x^\alpha) = 0, \quad \alpha = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4. \quad (8)$$

The following theorem is valid.

Theorem 1. The optimal coefficients for the quadrature formulas of the form (6) in the Sobolev space $L_2^{(m)}(-1, 1)$ are defined as follows

$$\dot{C}_{k-1,i}[0] = h^{-1} \left[F_{k-1,i}[1] - F_{k-1,i}[0] + \frac{h}{2} \left(\frac{g_{k-1,i}}{(k-1)!} - \nu_{k-2,i} \right) \right],$$

$$\dot{C}_{k-1,i}[\beta] = h^{-1} \left[F_{k-1,i}[\beta-1] - 2F_{k-1,i}[\beta] + F_{k-1,i}[\beta+1] \right], \quad \text{for } \beta = 1, \dots, N-1$$

$$\dot{C}_{k-1,i}[N] = h^{-1} \left[F_{k-1,i}[N-1] - F_{k-1,i}[N] + \frac{h}{2} \left(\frac{g_{k-1,i}}{(k-1)!} - \nu_{k-2,i} \right) \right],$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1$, where

$$\nu_{k-2,i} = \sum_{\alpha=0}^{k-2} \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_{\alpha,i}[\gamma] \frac{(h\gamma)^{k-\alpha-1}}{(k-\alpha-1)!},$$

$F_{k-1,i}$ and $g_{k-1,i}$ are known.

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